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THE CONCEPTION OF MONEY IN THE ESL CLASSROOM

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Abstract. *Learning English currently demands the application of appropriate modern methods and techniques for constructing students' incentive and motivation for productive studies. Undoubtedly, the application of real-life scenarios and providing students with tasks targeting their creative and strategic thinking leads to a better engagement on the lessons, which as a result serves as a fuel for the learners' productivity on the lessons of studying English as a second language. This paper discusses the utilization of the conception of money in the ESL classroom, providing an insight into students' attitudes towards the matter and explaining the results of the research conducted. The research consisted of gathering qualitative and quantitative data, with the use of a survey and observation, additionally demonstrating some of the samples of the way the concept of money may be used on the lessons of learning English as a second language. We are of the view that the utilization of the conception of money in the ESL classroom presents benefits for learning and may lead to students' increased productivity on the lessons.*

Keywords: *English language, ESL, the concept of money, learning methods, learning techniques.*

Introduction

Learning requires a reasonable amount of attention and productivity, which in turn requires appropriate tasks which are able to stimulate students' flexible thinking and engagement on the lessons. Creative tasks help achieve the given purpose, as thinking in a non-standard way promotes active participation on the lessons and provides students with a space for creating something of their own, without any limitations or strict rules for the way an exercise should be conducted and completed.

Creativity is the process of turning imaginative ideas into reality [1, p. 93]. The cause of creative tasks working well for students' activity and productivity is the amount of freedom they allow learners to use to express their thoughts and make it as personalized as possible. Constructing learners' foundation of grammar and vocabulary knowledge is the most important part of learning any language – however, the process of achieving it consists not only of monotonously doing a set of standardized similar exercises, but rather challenging students to apply innovative, problem-solving mindset, apply strategic thought processes. It may only be possible if we as teachers assign appropriate tasks which allow learners to utilize their unconventional viewpoints and paths to solving hypothetical exercises.

As money is one of the most fundamental parts of our world, applying its concept in the space of ESL classroom may be an engaging method to improve students' active participation on the lessons, as it directly correlates to segments of real life outside of the walls of an educational institution. The use of the conception of money may be viewed as a form of educational play. Guided play in ESL classrooms has been proven its effectiveness [2, p. 372]. Providing students with tasks which require them to count money, distribute it and make strategic decisions may increase students' engagement and productivity due to them actively applying their imagination and considering fictional issues from their personal viewpoints, demonstrating the variability of students' perspectives and using different ways to solve task problems.

Participation is an integral part of learning which orients the learner to explore further and contribute meaningfully to the classroom dynamics [3, p. 32]. Active participation on the lessons affect the learners' overall academic performance during the studying process, as being present and attentive in the classroom promotes better understanding of the studying material. We are of the

viewpoints that using the concept of money and assigning students with tasks based on it may affect learners' efficiency in the ESL classroom.

Methods

We began our research by selecting a study group consisting of 22 students learning English as a second language. Beginning with a conduction of a survey, we determined to inspect the learners' perspective on the issue at hand.

The first question of the survey was used to scrutinize the learners' general attitude towards creative tasks.

Table 1. The survey's first questions' results

Do you think creative tasks improve your efficiency and performance on the lessons?		
Yes	No	Have difficulty answering this questions
15 students (68.18%)	4 students (18.18%)	3 students (13.64%)

Based on the received results, we may draw a conclusion that a vast majority of learners consider tasks stimulating creativity to be a useful tool for increasing their efficiency and academic performance, with 15 students (68.18%) voting for the positive response, with 4 students (18.18%) disagreeing and 3 students (13.64%) having difficulty responding to the given question.

In our second questions we wanted to see what were the students' preferred forms of creative tasks.

Table 2. The survey's second question's results

Which form of creative tasks do you prefer?				
Creative writing tasks	Role-play tasks	Project-based creative tasks	Strategic thinking tasks	Multimedia tasks
2 students (9.09%)	6 students (27.27%)	2 students (9.09%)	7 students (31.82%)	5 students (22.73%)

Seeing results, we may conclude that the predominant number of students prefer role-play and strategic thinking tasks, with 6 students (27.27%) voting for exercises based on acting and performing and 7 students (31.82%) selecting a variant of strategic thinking tasks, with several students making up 22.73% of the whole number of participants demonstrating interest towards multimedia tasks.

Our third question was determined to inspect students' viewpoints as to why they consider creative tasks to be effective for their learning process and increasing their engagement and participation during class.

Table 3. The survey's third question's results

Why do you think creative tasks improve your engagement and productivity on the lessons?				
Using our imagination stimulates our brain	I feel freer during this type of tasks, not restricted by typical rules and limitations	Because we use English for real life situations and the correlation between exercises and actual life conditions stimulate my interest	These tasks reduce stress	I don't consider this type of tasks to be improving my engagement and performance during class
2 students (9.09%)	9 students (40.91%)	4 students (18.18%)	2 students (9.09%)	5 students (22.73%)

Based on the results received, we can see that the majority of the participants of the research consider creative exercises to be beneficial for their engagement and productivity levels during class as they sense freedom during the conduction of this type of tasks, not being restricted by various limitations which may be presented in a standard type of exercises usually applied in the classroom, with 9 students (40.91%) voting for the mentioned variant.

In our final question, we determine to learn the students' viewpoint on whether they think an application of tasks related to the conception of money would be useful for increasing their efficiency and active participation during class.

Table 4. The survey's fourth question's results

Do you think money-related creative tasks would increase your productivity and incentive on the lessons?		
Yes	No	Have difficulty answering the questions
14 students (63.64%)	3 students (13.64%)	5 students (22.73%)

The survey's fourth questions' results illustrate the generally positive attitude towards application of creative tasks based on the utilization of the concept of money, with 14 students (63.64%) voting for the positive variant, 3 students (13.64%) disagreeing and 5 students (22.73%) having difficulty responding the questions. Overall, the survey showed the preparedness of the learners to work on creative tasks related to the concept of money.

In order to monitor progress of the students, we applied observation for 4 weeks of the research, conducting the final interview of the participants in the end to gather their concluding viewpoints towards the matter.

Discussion

As mentioned before, creative tasks assist lecturers in increasing students' engagement and academic performance during class. The application of exercises based on the utilization of the concept of money may be beneficial due to its direct correlation to real life conditions.

One of the sample tasks which a teacher may use during class is based on providing the learners with a certain problem task. For instance, a theme under study may be related to cities, living conditions, society – a task with the use of the conception of money may require students to divide into teams and consider how they would spend a certain budget for improving a city, with various aspects being presented to them, as parks and recreation, educational institutions, etc. In particular, they may be told that they are given 10 million of dollars and they need to decide on how they would distribute it among various aspects of the city improvement.

Table 5. Sample task

You have 10 million dollars to improve your city. How would you distribute it between the given aspects?				
Parks and recreation	Educational institutions	Safety	New buildings	Digitalization

The given type of tasks promotes strategic thinking, as well as collaborative learning altogether as a result of working in a team. In the contemporary, swiftly changing environment, it is essential for students to acquire 21st-century skills, making collaborative learning particularly relevant [4, p. 37].

Another sample of a money-related task possible for use in the ESL classroom is providing students with an exercise on the theme of making gifts, which is appropriate for themes as family, gifts or holidays. A task may provide students with descriptions of people presenting various desirable products and object – however, each student has a limited budget, which in turn consists of money they «earned» during a quiz conducted beforehand. The points they received during the quiz serves

as the amount of money they have available for fictional charity. The given task promotes strategic and creative thinking as well.

Furthermore, a sample of this type of tasks may be based on fictional grocery shopping or shopping for apartment renovation, while also having a limited budget for each of the students, with the tasks being oriented both for individual and team-based conduction.

The composition of tasks which are related to the conception of money is reasonably flexible, with the idea of money being appropriate for any type of theme students may examine at a moment, as finances is an integral fragment of real life.

During the observation process, we took notice that including money-related creative tasks indeed improved students active participation and engagement on the lessons, as applying strategic thinking and sensing freedom in the way they could distribute fictional money and present their perspective for the problem tasks stimulated their creativity and personal approach for fictional issues at hand.

To inspect the accurate views of the students, we conducted the final face-to-face interview with the participants of the research, consisting of 3 questions.

Table 6. The first question of the final interview of the students

Do you think the inclusion of money-related creative tasks improved your engagement and productivity levels on the lessons?		
Yes	No	Have difficulty answering the question
18 students (81.82%)	2 students (9.09%)	2 students (9.09%)

In the end of the research, the predominant number of the students responded that in their viewpoint, the application of money-related exercises increased their engagement and productivity levels during class, which coincides with our personal observation conducted.

We proceeded with the second questions to determine as to why they consider the tasks related to the conception of money to be effective in improving their engagement on the lessons.

Table 7. The second question of the final interview of the students

Why do you think money-related exercises improved your engagement and productivity during class?		
Due to the relation to real life conditions	Due to applying strategic thinking, which was engaging to me	The tasks did not improve my performance during class
9 students (40.91%)	11 students (50%)	2 students (9.09%)

The results illustrate that the prevalent number of students consider that the creative tasks based on the use of the concept of money were effective in increasing their participation and academic performance during class due to the utilization of strategic thinking being an engaging form of learning to them, with 11 students (50%) voting for the given variant and 9 students (40.91%) naming the reason being the relation of the tasks to real life conditions, with 2 students (9.09%) concluding that the tasks did not increase their productivity during class.

Our final question was used to determine combination between which form of creative types of tasks and exercises related to the concept of money they would want to be applied more in the classroom.

Table 8. The third question of the final interview of the students

Combination between which form of creative tasks and money-related exercises would you want to be applied in the classroom?				
Role-play	Creative writing	Multimedia tasks	Project-based tasks	Have difficulty answering

13 students (59.09%)	2 students (9.09%)	5 students (22.73%)	1 student (4.55%)	1 student (4.55%)
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From the table above, we can see that the predominant part of the learners demonstrates interested in seeing a combination between money-related exercises and acting tasks, as well as some interest towards the merge between multimedia and tasks based on the concept of money.

Results

We may conclude that based on the observation and final interview conducted, the use of creative exercises based on the application of the conception of money is beneficial for increasing students' active engagement on the lessons, which subsequently improves their academic performance during class.

Recommendations

We recommend lecturers to combine exercises based on the use of the concept of money with various existing creative forms of learning tasks to make the exercises more challenging and engaging for the students. Furthermore, the issue at hand would benefit from continued research, as the theme under study, as of now, has not been studied enough yet.

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